

LET'S EMPOWER TEACHERS, TRANSFORM CLASS ROOMS, SCHOOLS AND COMMUNITY AS A WHOLE

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Y Personal
qualities

X

Professional
knowledge

Z

Experience

Quality of Teaching $Q = XYZ$

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Quality Classroom Transactions by use of Modern Resources

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ONE are the days when teachers were teaching using chalk and talk method. Most of the teacher educators like us use to record in our observation diary that the student-teachers i.e. would be teachers in teacher education programmes make use of Daily Using Teaching Aids (DUTA). By this we meant that the student teachers were practicing their lessons using Chalk, Duster, Blackboard; and followed 'Lecture Method' for teaching and the primary source behind lesson preparation was generally textbook prescribed by the state board. Thus, teacher's innovation was limited to ways of expression restricting to tone, gestures, drawing skills on the board with different colour chalk pieces and a rolling blackboard containing few assignment activities. If a teacher was not good at handwriting and/or drawing then a shabby picture was projected in front of the students that demoralised practicing teacher. Some of the creative and artistic teachers used to bring well prepared charts and models relevant to the transactional content. This was followed by a period when students got access to the Internet. The creative student-teachers were found to print relevant pictures on different sizes of paper. They also made black and white print colourful using different colour shades and outlines as prints and thus it became more economical compared to hiring of artists for preparation of charts. These efforts were praiseworthy too as in a short span of 9 months duration of the programme the students were

supposed to complete 40 lessons in two different subjects. This was in addition to reading of entirely different content of syllabus in education discipline for theory examination. Thus, theory contents of teacher education programmes were different from their basic discipline that is Arts, Science, Commerce, etc. which overburdened student teachers in shorter duration.

Now, the situation has changed and many resources have emerged for the use of student teachers. The textbook is not 'the only source of information' for student teachers. The Departments of Education, State Council of Educational Research and Training (SCERTs), National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) are preparing supplementary materials for teachers. There is also a flood gate of resources opened for teachers or student teacher trainees in the form of private publications for particular age group of students, which also act as resources for teachers too. Based on the pattern

which is followed by school, school learning material is available, that means the material is available for state, CBSE, ICSE pattern, transdisciplinary programme like International Baccalaureate programmes etc. There are various other age specific, enrichment books, which provide additional information for student teachers, teachers and school students as well. Thus, the scope of thinking and pondering horizons of student teachers have increased manifold. This is why the increased duration of teacher education programme especially B.Ed., as laid down by new regulations of teacher education (2014) provide ample opportunities to student teachers to practice innovations. The compulsory internship helps to know School facilities and optimally use them by gaining in-depth understanding.

The new regulations of teacher education laid down by NCTE in 2014 have also emphasized use of

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Information Communication Technologies (ICTs) as an integral part of teacher education programme at all level. The innovations in ICTs have made teacher trainees updated, as they get latest versions of information from different parts of the globe through Internet. To be specific the content based resources are available in different formats like text, image, audio, video etc. It is the effort and attempts of teachers who can pool different sources at a particular place to meet needs of a learner for quality education. From the point of view of a practising classroom student teacher, it should not be a matter of great worry that the material obtained is a copyrighted material or open resource for use in classroom. Because teacher's intention is to impart knowledge

to classroom learner and they do not intend to claim somebody else's product as their own. The deliberations are as good as preparation by teachers before they go to class by understanding various aspects of concepts to be taught. It is however, to be noted here that if the teacher intends to record or publish the material then licensing provided by original author may be strictly taken care. Bringing such materials together from different resources to attain educational objectives forms part of the process called 'Blended Learning'. Such learning provides opportunity for appealing more than one sense and provides variety in learning with experts from various fields.

A well aware, experienced doctor diagnoses his patient properly and suggest appropriate medications, so also more learned well aware teacher can employ proper teaching methods in the classroom to improve quality education. To summarise access to abundant educational resources

enhances teacher awareness and increases his or her expertise and experience for bringing quality education to their disciples.

I have observed that some of the student teachers, teacher educator also use messages received in informal WhatsApp groups during classroom academic deliberations. Thus, now individual learning is not restricted only to sources like text books for social interactions, but it goes beyond classical teaching sources. Thus, use of WhatsApp for academic purposes has also added new dimension for sharing of resources for a classroom teacher. If multiple resources in the form of multimedia are used, then learning can be enhanced under improved transaction quality.

Textbooks from various state and national boards are accessible to student-teachers at a click of button and they need not go for purchase of books to shops or market. These provisions give broader perspectives for reader as he or she can understand more regarding ways of presentation

of contents for similar age group learners in different formats. Few government offices who hosts their material on their websites for the benefit of learner are SCERT Kerala, DESERT, Bangalore, NCERT, New Delhi, NIOS, New Delhi etc.

Large number of the government and private publishers are supplying CDs along with the textbooks. The textbooks also indicate about URL which the learner can go for further information. Thus, these enrichment bits for readers help in meeting requirements of gifted children. The overall examination of availability of abundant academic resources leads us for quality classroom transaction in schools of modern era.

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